

Students' Perceptions of Generative Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education

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Abstract

The rapid development of information technologies, accelerated by the pandemic, has significantly increased the presence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in higher education. Although AI has long been embedded in many educational tools, our surveys show that students, including those in informatics programs, often lack a clear understanding of its mechanisms, possibilities, and limitations. Through two questionnaire-based studies, we examined the extent to which students adopt AI for learning, writing academic assignments, and programming, and their expectations regarding the proper use of these technologies. The findings reveal that, despite their technical proficiency, students' adoption of AI is uneven and largely intuitive, often without awareness of underlying principles or ethical considerations. At the same time, students express a strong need for formal education that would enable them to use AI safely, effectively, and responsibly in their academic work. The results confirm that universities should play an active role in guiding AI usage and building competencies that support its responsible integration into the educational process. Based on survey results, we identify key advantages and disadvantages of AI adoption in universities and provide recommendations for its effective implementation in academic environments.

Keywords

AI Adoption; Higher Education; AI in Learning; Educational Technology; Responsible AI Use; Digital Literacy

1 Introduction

The release of large language models such as ChatGPT, Gemini, or Claude significantly accelerated the integration of AI tools into higher education. Although AI technologies have long been embedded in search engines, recommendation systems, and learning platforms, the public accessibility of generative AI (GenAI) has fundamentally transformed students' interaction with digital tools.

Empirical evidence suggests that student adoption of generative AI is both rapid and widespread. According to the Higher Education Policy Institute (Freeman, 2025) Student Generative AI Survey, approximately 88% of UK students report using generative AI tools in some form to support their studies. Importantly, the survey highlights a significant discrepancy between the speed of student adoption and the level of formal institutional guidance. While students perceive AI as increasingly important for academic success, structured training and clear policies often remain limited.

Similarly, research conducted by Jisc (Attewell, 2025) confirms that AI tools have become deeply integrated into students' everyday academic routines. However, alongside enthusiasm, students also express concerns regarding misinformation, declining quality of work, overreliance

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on automation, privacy risks, and long-term employability implications. These findings indicate that AI adoption is not merely a technological shift but also a pedagogical and ethical challenge.

A global perspective is provided by the Digital Education Council (Digital Education Council, 2024) Global AI Student Survey, which reports consistently high adoption rates across multiple countries. The survey emphasizes that students expect universities to play an active role in defining acceptable use, offering training, and ensuring responsible implementation. Thus, international evidence suggests that while AI usage is largely student-driven, governance and strategic direction are expected from institutions.

While existing international surveys and policy frameworks provide valuable macro-level insights into the adoption of generative AI in higher education, empirical evidence from Central and Eastern European contexts remains limited. Little attention has been paid to informatics-oriented students, who constitute a distinctive group due to their advanced digital literacy and frequent use of AI tools. This study contributes to the current discourse by contextualizing global findings within the Slovak higher education environment and by offering discipline-specific insight into AI usage patterns, ethical awareness, and expectations regarding institutional guidance. Rather than proposing a new theoretical adoption model, the paper provides empirically grounded evidence that refines and situates international trends within a specific national and disciplinary setting.

1.1 Students' Perceptions: Benefits, Risks, and Usage Patterns

Beyond adoption rates, recent studies have examined how students perceive and practically use generative AI tools.

Chan and Hu (Chan and Hu, 2023), in their study *Students' Voices on Generative AI*, surveyed 399 university students in Hong Kong and identified several perceived benefits of GenAI, including:

- personalized academic support,
- brainstorming assistance,
- explanation of complex concepts,
- support in research and writing tasks.

However, the study also highlighted concerns about accuracy, ethical misuse, academic integrity, and long-term societal impacts. Students recognized both the utility and potential risks of AI, demonstrating a nuanced perception rather than unconditional acceptance.

Mohammad et al. (Mohammad et al., 2025) provide further insight into practical usage patterns, identifying common applications such as drafting assignments, summarizing texts, generating ideas, debugging code, and clarifying theoretical concepts. These usage patterns align closely with findings from our survey, in which students predominantly reported using AI for programming, web research, and software-related tasks.

A broader synthesis is offered by Campbell University's *AI in Higher Education: A Meta Summary of Recent Surveys of Students and Faculty*, which aggregates multiple large-scale surveys (including HEPI and institutional studies). The meta-summary indicates that roughly 80% of students globally use generative AI to support learning. Notably, it also identifies a gap between students' generally positive attitudes and faculty members' more cautious perspectives.

Further evidence from *Inside Higher Ed* (Flaherty, 2025) suggests that students do not perceive AI as diminishing the value of higher education. Instead, AI changes how they conceptualize learning and academic work. While some express concern about critical thinking skills, many report that AI can enhance understanding when used appropriately.

Collectively, these studies indicate that AI adoption among students is neither purely instrumental nor purely problematic. Rather, it is characterized by pragmatic usage, perceived efficiency gains, and ongoing ethical uncertainty.

While studies on perception are abundant, the question of whether AI positively or negatively affects learning outcomes remains central. A comprehensive meta-analysis conducted by Wang et al. (H. Wang et al., 2024), published within *Nature Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, examined 51 empirical studies from 2022–2024. The analysis found:

- a large positive effect on learning performance,
- a moderate positive effect on learning perception,
- a moderate positive effect on higher-order thinking skills.

Importantly, the study emphasizes that the educational impact of ChatGPT and similar tools depends heavily on instructional design, duration of use, and pedagogical integration. AI demonstrates the strongest positive effects when embedded in structured learning environments rather than used as an unsupervised shortcut.

This finding is particularly relevant to our research. Although our survey indicates widespread AI use among IT students, it also reveals an uneven understanding of the underlying principles and limited awareness of ethical considerations. The literature suggests that without pedagogical framing, the potential cognitive benefits of AI may not be fully realized.

1.2 Empirical Study: AI Usage Among IT Students at the University of Economics in Bratislava

To complement international findings on AI adoption in higher education, we conducted an empirical study focused on students enrolled in informatics-oriented programs at the University of Economics in Bratislava, Slovakia. The objective was to examine students' awareness of AI technologies, their actual usage patterns in academic contexts, and their perceptions regarding potential AI applications within university educational and managerial processes.

1.2.1 Research Design and Methodology

The study was conducted between September and November 2024 using a structured questionnaire distributed electronically to students of:

- Economic Informatics (Bachelor's level), and
- Information Management (Master's level).

Although more than 300 students were invited to participate, we obtained 48 valid responses. The questionnaire consisted of 12 questions combining single-choice, multiple-choice, and open-ended items. The questions addressed:

- general attitudes toward AI usage at the university,
- perceived usefulness of AI tools,
- specific areas where AI could improve university processes,
- personal usage of AI tools in academic work,
- perceived advantages and risks of ChatGPT and similar models.

A primary limitation of this study is the relatively small sample size ($n = 48$), which limits statistical generalizability. The findings should therefore be interpreted as exploratory rather than representative of the broader higher education population.

However, the focused and homogeneous nature of the sample informatics-oriented students enhances contextual relevance. As future IT professionals with high exposure to digital technologies, this group provides meaningful insight into AI adoption patterns within a clearly defined disciplinary environment. The study thus prioritizes contextual depth over broad generalization.

Additionally, the cross-sectional design captures perceptions and usage patterns at a single point in time amid rapid technological development. Future research will expand the dataset and incorporate a longitudinal follow-up to strengthen generalizability and track changes in AI adoption over time.

1.2.2 General Attitudes Toward AI in University Processes

Most respondents indicated that AI could improve university processes (Figure 1). However, several students emphasized that the benefits would depend heavily on the quality of implementation. This conditional support reflects a pragmatic rather than idealistic view of technological integration.

When asked which technologies would be appropriate for university use, students most frequently suggested:

- chatbots,
- machine learning methods,
- rule-based systems,
- augmented and virtual reality solutions.

Chatbots were perceived as particularly suitable for administrative support functions, especially in the study office context.

Figure 1. Process improvement by AI at the university (Own processing)

1.2.3 Perceived Applications of Chatbots

Among the 48 respondents, chatbot usage was most frequently suggested for:

- answering frequently asked questions (79.2%),
- providing general study information (77.1%),

- supplying information about subjects and syllabi (72.9%),
- consultation hours and contact details (60.4%),
- academic calendar information (56.3%).

These responses indicate that students associate AI primarily with operational efficiency and information accessibility rather than with strategic or pedagogical transformation.

Interestingly, one respondent explicitly suggested that AI could support “more effective learning with critical evaluation of gained information,” demonstrating awareness of AI’s potential educational role beyond administrative support. Below are students’ responses to the suggested tools (Figure 2).

■ What technologies and tools would you suggest?

Figure 2. AI tools suggested by the students (Own processing)

Most respondents reported using some form of AI in their studies. ChatGPT was by far the most frequently mentioned tool. Other tools included:

- Bing AI,
- Bard,
- GitHub Copilot,
- PhotoMath,
- DeepL,
- automated syntax correction systems in programming environments.

Students most commonly used AI for:

- web research,
- programming tasks,
- working with various software tools (over 55% in each category).

A smaller proportion reported using AI for:

- writing assignments,
- verifying information,

Figure 3. Usage of AI tools (Own processing)

- mathematical problem solving.

Only a very small number of respondents reported not using AI at all. We can see the findings in Figure 3.

These findings align with international evidence indicating that AI adoption is particularly strong in technical and programming-related contexts (Mohammad et al., 2025; Chan and Hu, 2023).

1.2.4 Perception of ChatGPT as a Learning Tool

Approximately two-thirds of respondents considered ChatGPT to be a suitable learning tool. However, students also demonstrated awareness of important limitations. Key concerns included:

1. The need to verify information due to possible inaccuracies.
2. Limited contextual understanding of the model.
3. The importance of not replacing human interaction and traditional learning resources.

This nuanced perception suggests that students do not view AI as a substitute for education, but rather as a supplementary tool; this is consistent with broader international findings (J. Wang and Fan, 2025).

2 Conclusion

The rapid diffusion of AI tools in higher education has prompted international organizations to develop governance frameworks.

The UNESCO (Miao, Holmes, et al., 2021) publication, *AI and Education: Guidance for Policy-makers*, emphasizes the inclusive, human-centered integration of AI into educational systems. Key principles include:

- development of AI literacy,
- teacher training,
- ethical safeguards,
- protection of privacy and data,
- equitable access to technology.

More specifically, UNESCO's *Guidance for Generative AI in Education and Research* (Miao and Holmes, 2026) addresses generative AI tools directly, highlighting the need for ethical

validation, transparency, human oversight, and protection against overreliance on automated systems.

Complementing this perspective, the OECD AI Principles (Russo and Oder, 2023) define international standards for trustworthy AI, emphasizing human-centered values, robustness, transparency, accountability, and safety. These principles provide a normative framework for institutional AI governance.

Institutional policy analysis by Wang (H. Wang et al., 2024) further shows that universities worldwide are still developing coherent AI policies. Many institutions adopt reactive strategies, issuing guidelines after widespread student adoption has already occurred. This mirrors findings from our own survey context, where AI usage appears to have outpaced formal institutional regulation.

Key Findings and Identified Gaps

Despite being informatics students, respondents revealed several knowledge gaps:

- Many were unable to clearly distinguish between augmented and virtual reality.
- A significant number did not fully understand that they already use AI daily (e.g., search engines, MS Office tools, developer software, translation systems).
- Students often associate AI exclusively with specific subjects such as “Artificial Intelligence” or “Machine Learning,” rather than recognizing its broader systemic integration.

Furthermore, when asked about AI’s role in managerial university processes (e.g., enrollment, Erasmus mobility, financial procedures), many students demonstrated limited awareness of institutional workflows. This suggests that students’ AI-related thinking is primarily tool-oriented rather than process-oriented.

Our findings indicate that AI adoption among IT students is:

- widespread but largely intuitive,
- operational rather than strategic,
- tool-focused rather than principle-based,
- accompanied by limited awareness of governance and ethical implications.

Even within a technically proficient population, AI literacy regarding underlying mechanisms, risks, and institutional processes remains incomplete.

At the same time, students expressed openness to formal AI-related education and recognized the potential benefits of structured implementation. This confirms international calls for universities to assume an active role in developing AI competencies (Miao, Holmes, et al., 2021; Miao and Holmes, 2026; Russo and Oder, 2023).

The present study provides an initial empirical insight into AI adoption among informatics-oriented students within the Slovak higher education context. Future research should focus on expanding the sample size and including additional cohorts of IT students to strengthen statistical robustness and improve the stability of the findings.

A key direction for further investigation involves the planned longitudinal follow-up. Repeated data collection over time would enable examination of evolving AI usage patterns, shifts in ethical awareness, and changes in students’ expectations regarding institutional regulation and guidance. Considering the rapid development of generative AI technologies and the gradual establishment of university-level policies, a longitudinal design would provide valuable insight into the dynamics of AI adoption in higher education.

Future studies may also explore relationships between AI usage intensity, academic performance, digital competencies, and attitudes toward responsible AI use. Integrating qualitative methods, such as interviews or focus groups, could further enrich the understanding of students' motivations and decision-making processes when using AI tools.

Implications for Higher Education Institutions

Drawing on both our empirical findings and international frameworks, universities should:

- integrate AI literacy into curricula across disciplines,
- establish transparent institutional policies on acceptable AI use,
- provide systematic training for academic staff,
- implement pilot AI-supported learning initiatives with ongoing evaluation,
- maintain human oversight in assessment and decision-making processes.

The literature consistently indicates that AI is not inherently detrimental to learning. Rather, its impact depends on governance, pedagogical design, and responsible integration. Institutions that proactively address these dimensions are more likely to harness AI's educational benefits while mitigating associated risks.

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